

Synthesis of 3-Substituted-amino/aryloxy-7-chloro-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-ones as Possible Anxiolytics

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Ten new 3-substituted-amino/aryloxy-7-chloro-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-ones were synthesised and tested for their acute toxicity, effect on gross behaviour and anxiolytic activity using antihypoxia and antimetrazole tests in mice. At 1/5th ALD₅₀, two compounds, one with a morpholino group and the other with a 4-methoxybenzoyloxy group at 3-position exhibited maximum antimetrazole activity similar to oxazepam and also produced significant increase of survival time in antihypoxia test which was comparable to oxazepam.

THE structure activity relationship on 1,4-benzodiazepines had been studied^{1,2}. The introduction of a hydroxy, alkoxy, carboxy *etc.* groups at 3-position had yielded the compounds with significant anxiolytic activity. Esterification of 3-hydroxy group also resulted into compounds with similar activity since the hydrolysis at the ester linkage produced the parent compound as a metabolite. Moreover, several esters and amides of 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzoic acid also possessed high tranquillising activity^{3,4}. These reports prompted the authors to synthesise the title compounds with an amine residue or an aryloxy group at 3-position of 1,4-benzodiazepine moiety and to evaluate them for their anxiolytic activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The reactions were followed by tlc. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord and Perkin-Elmer 177 or 137 grating instruments as KBr discs. Pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A60D spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

5-Chloro-3-phenylanthranil⁵, 2-amino-5-chlorobenzophenone⁶, 2-amino-5-chlorobenzophenone

oxime⁶, 2-chloroacetamido-5-chlorobenzophenone oxime⁶, 2-chloromethyl-4-phenyl-6-chloroquinazoline-3-oxide⁶, 7-chloro-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one-4-oxide⁷, 3-acetoxy-7-chloro-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one⁸ and 7-chloro-3-hydroxy-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one⁸ were prepared by the known procedures.

3-Substituted-amino-7-chloro-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-ones (1-4): To a solution of 7-chloro-3-hydroxy-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one (0.001 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) were added appropriate amine (0.0011 mol) and two drops of glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was heated at reflux for 18-24 h and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol in yields 50-80%. The compounds were characterised by their m.ps., elemental analyses and ir spectral data which showed the presence of bands at 3 400-3 200 (amide NH), 2 900 (CH₂), 1 670 (amide C=O) and 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

3-Aryloxy-7-chloro-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-ones (7-10): To a suspension of an aroyl chloride (0.0015 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) were added 7-chloro-3-hydroxy-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.004 mol). The mixture was then refluxed for 8-12 h on a water-bath. Triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was recrystallised from aqueous methanol or benzene-petroleum ether mixture in yields 80-95%. The compounds were characterised by their m.ps., elemental analyses and ir bands at 3 150 (amide NH),

TABLE I—3-SUBSTITUTED-AMINO/AROYLOXY-7-CHLORO-5-PHENYL-1,3-DIHYDRO-2H-1,4-BENZODIAZEPIN-2-ONES*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	ALD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p. (confidence limit)	Anxiolytic activity ^a % increase in survival time
1	Morpholino	175-76	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂	681 (nil)	33.33
2	Dimethylamino	151-52	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O	825 (562-1210)	13.66
3	N-Phenylpiperazino	129-30	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O	825 (562-1210)	—
4	Piperidino	105-06	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O	681 (nil)	16.39
5	N-Methylpiperazino	111-12	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O	681 (nil)	—
6	3,4,5-Trimethoxyanilino	116-18	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₄	681 (nil)	16.75
7 ^b	Benzoyloxy	220-21	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	681 (nil)	—
8	4-Methoxybenzoyloxy	178-79	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₄	681 (nil)	35.59
9	3,4,5-Trimethoxybenzoyloxy	112-13	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₆	>1000	—
10	4-Nitrobenzoyloxy	229-30	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₃	825 (562-1210)	20.54
	Oxazepam	—	—	825 (562-1210)	59.28

* All compounds analysed for C, H and N were found satisfactory.

^a δ (CDCl₃) 8.50 (1H, m, NH), 7.80-7.90 (13H, m, ArH) and 4.80 (1H, s, COCHOCO). ^b Mean survival time for control groups ranged from 33.4 to 37.6 min. At 1/5th ALD₅₀, no gross behavioural effect was observed in compounds while oxazepam was depressant. At 1/5th ALD₅₀, 1, 8 and oxazepam were 100% active while 9 was 60% active against metrazole induced seizures.

2 950 (CH aliphatic), 1 730 (ester C=O), 1 680 (amide C=O) and 1 625 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Pharmacological studies: Acute toxicity studies (LD₅₀ determination)⁹, gross behavioural effects¹⁰ and anxiolytic activity by metrazole seizure threshold test¹¹ (a model^{12,13} for preliminary screening of anxiolytic activity) and antihypoxia test¹⁴ were carried out by known procedures. Oxazepam was used as standard in all these tests. The results have been summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

ALD₅₀ of compounds 1 and 4-8 was 681 mg/kg while for 2, 3, 10 and oxazepam it was 825 mg/kg. Compound 9 had an ALD₅₀ > 1 000 mg/kg. At 1/5th ALD₅₀ none of the test compounds showed any effect on gross behaviour while oxazepam had depressant effect. The significant increase in survival time¹⁵ and protection against metrazole seizures by 1, 8 and oxazepam had shown that they had appreciable anxiolytic activity. Compounds 1 and 8 were, however, devoid of CNS depression. Compound 9 produced 60% protection against metrazole seizures. Among the 3-substituted-amino compounds (1-6) only the morpholino compound (1) was active and the activity might be attributed to the internal ether linkage¹⁵ present in morpholine. Anxiolytic activity of compounds 8 and 9 confirmed the structure activity relationship studies that esterification of 3-hydroxy group retained the activity while lack of activity in 7 and 10 suggested that hydrolysis at ester linkage might not be occurring to yield oxazepam as metabolite. Complete loss of activity in 6 and less activity in 9 had indicated that introduction of a trimethoxyphenyl group was not desirable.

Thus, 7-chloro-5-phenyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one with a 3-(4-morpholino) group (1)

or a 3-(4-methoxybenzoyloxy) group (8) possess anxiolytic activity comparable to oxazepam. They are, however, devoid of CNS depression, a distinct advantage over oxazepam.

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